

Silvopasture and Agrovoltaics

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Sheep grazing to manage the pastures under photovoltaic panels in an integrated way, in Agrogestiona farm, Granada

Optimizing the use of the resources to increase the ecological, economic and social provision benefits by using silvopasture is a sustainable strategy for livestock and agrovoltaics management in Mediterranean grazing systems that provides renewable energy. Silvopasture in Andalusia also promotes economic, environmental and social benefits as the integrated management reduces costs, both in terms of feeding the animals and maintaining the cleanliness of the solar infrastructure (reducing dust associated with the lack of a vegetation cover), which together with adequate stocking rates and grazing planning, increases production and allows a more effective use of the available area, avoiding land degradation.

Adequate livestock stocking rates play a key role sustaining silvopasture systems improving soil health and reducing overgrazing to ensure permanent grasslands regeneration based on annual species in Mediterranean systems while increasing organic matter and microbial biodiversity. Healthier soils linked to adequate stocking rates improve biodiversity (longer grassland permanence benefiting auxiliary fauna), water retention and fertility due to the promotion of soil cover, reducing soil erosion which returns in a better quality and higher quantity forage providing better resilience to climatic change.

Grazed silvopasture agrovoltaic challenges are related to the need of high land parcelling, implying high investment in fencing and water points.

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